

PEDAGOGICAL BASIS OF EDUCATION CLASSIFICATION

Omarova Gavhar Sadikovna

Researcher at Bukhara State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8214276>

Abstract. The article analyzes the pedagogical basis of educational differentiation, and classifies its specific features and the form of differential education.

Keywords: differentiation, education, perception, person-oriented education, individualization, interest.

Introduction. Perception is such a form of our knowledge that it ensures that we reflect the object we need at the moment with its properties and characteristics among many, diverse objects and events in existence. That is, perception is based on a unified image of things and events, which is different from others. Perception, as we mentioned above, consists of sensory processes, similar to the sound of a clock, which is simpler than itself [1].

Differentiation (stratification) is derived from the Latin language and means differentiation, separation. The need for differentiation arises from the diversity of thinking abilities of students. Without differentiation in the classroom (classroom), the learning process is organized the same for all students and is effective for them in different ways. And the general intellectual abilities of students are different, and their ability to learn is different: someone can learn new material very quickly, someone needs more time to consolidate it, needs to repeat more to master it, for someone the ability to hear new information is better, for someone the ability to see.

There are students who have well-developed logical thinking and natural-mathematical form, but they are not interested in the humanities. Or, on the contrary, he has a very well-developed creative imagination, a deep intuition, but... he is not interested in mathematics, physics and chemistry. Of course, you can train different people in the same way, but as a result, the quality of the training process will naturally decrease.

Differentiation of education allows us to organize the educational process based on the individual characteristics of the person, which ensures the mastery of the educational content with a fixed part for each student. In addition, each student of the group continues his path with students who have similar individual characteristics. Thus, the goal of the educational process differentiation is to create conditions for each student to satisfy his abilities,

inclinations, knowledge needs and interests in the process of mastering the general educational content.

In order to more clearly understand the essence of the differentiated (differential) approach, we can consider its three aspects:

1. Taking into account the individual characteristics of students;
2. Grouping of students taking into account these characteristics;
3. Variability of the learning process in groups.

The first aspect is characterized by both differentiation and individualization, taking into account the individual characteristics of students. Another distinctive feature of differentiated teaching is that grouping takes into account the individual characteristics of students and organizes a different learning process in these groups.

Individualization is the final variant of differentiation, in which the educational process is focused on organizing the learning process, taking into account the unique characteristics of each student, rather than groups.

Differentiation means a method of organizing the educational process that takes into account the individual and typological characteristics of a person (abilities, interests, inclinations, characteristics of intellectual activity, etc.). Classification is characterized by the creation of groups of students with different elements of the didactic system (goals, content, methods, forms, results).

In modern pedagogical literature, the concept of variation is often found, sometimes it is mixed with the concept of differentiation.

If changes in the content depend on the individual typological characteristics of students, it is legitimate to talk about differential learning. In this case, the students of each group learn the invariant content enriched with the necessary fragments for this group.

If changes in the structure of education are related to the preferences of the teacher, methodist, their views on this, then we are not talking about differentiation in education, but about variability

Recently, the term "person-oriented education" is often used in pedagogical literature. What does it have to do with stratification? Differentiation is one of the means of implementing student-centered learning.

Person-oriented education includes the construction of individual educational paths taking into account the subjective experience of a person, his preferences and values, actualization of personal functions of the student during the educational process.

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In the center of the educational process, a person becomes a person, the purpose of education includes the need for self-determination, self-discovery, and self-realization. Differential training helps to reveal individuality, to determine the abilities and inclinations of a person, includes updating the functions of personal choice.

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